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PRODUCTION, NUTRIENTS AND SENSORY EVALUATION OF OGI MADE FROM YELLOW MAIZE FORTIFIED WITH NATURAL ADDITIVES

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ABSTRACT

Ogi is a popular fermented staple cereal food commonly made from maize, sorghum, and millet. This research arises from the need to meet the demand of pregnant women and children of under five years in the rural and urban areas in Nigeria owing to the increase in the deficiency of mineral nutrient during pregnancy and early stage of growth of children. This study involves the production, nutrients and sensory evaluation of Ogi made from yellow maize fortified with natural additives (soy beans, date fruit, sunflower seed, ginger, mint leaf, beetroot and turmeric). The following formulations were made. Sample A (100: 0: 0: 0:0:0: 0:0), sample B (55:15:17:9:3:0.5:0:0.25), sample C (50:15:17:9:3:0.5:0:0.25), and sample D (45:25:17:9:3:0.5:0:0.25). The proximate, mineral, anti-nutrients, and sensory evaluation were determined using the standard methods of AOAC. The results were subjected to Analysis of Variance to determine the significant differences using Turkey's test. There was a statistical difference between each sample at $p < 0.05$. The result of the analyses obtained from the processed pap flour with additives indicates that the moisture, ash, protein fat, carbohydrates and crude fiber varied from (5.66-12.22%), (8.6 -10.35%), (4.35 - 9.40%), (2.0 - 4.39%), (78.09-50.74 %), (6.09-12.34%) respectively. A decrease in carbohydrate was observed with the

addition of natural additives. The mineral and anti-nutrient content increased with the addition of the blend; however, the anti-nutrient is within the acceptable level by FAO. The consumer acceptability test was carried out by 30 panelists and instant Ogi with MFSB (55% maize flour, 15% soy beans, 9% sunflower seed, 17% date fruit, 0.5% mint leaf, 0.25 turmeric, and 3% ginger) was rated best for the sample. This research opined that adequately fortified Ogi could reduce mineral nutrient deficiencies and higher reliance on expensive industrial products like custards.

KEYWORDS: Ogi, Nutrients, and Natural additives

INTRODUCTION

The Nigerian indigenous fermented foods constitute a group of foods that are produced in homes, villages and small-scale cottage industries. They are sold to the rural populace who buy them for food and social economies. The fermented foods are derived from substrates like roots, legumes, cereals, oil seeds, nuts, meat, fish, milk and palm tree sap (Oguntunde, 1989, Uzogara *et al.*, 1990). One of the indigenous fermented foods in Nigeria is Ogi, which is a fermented cereal porridge made from maize (*Zea mays*), sorghum (*Sorghum vulgare*) or millet). The Ogi is very smooth in texture with a sour taste similar to that of yoghurt (Banigoaqnd Muller, 1972). In Nigeria, the uncooked ogi is either prepared into a smooth porridge called pap or a solid gel known as “Eko” or “Agidi”. The consistency of the pap varies from thick to watery. The pap can be sweetened with sugar, milk or their combination and it is then eaten with beans cake or other foods. Onyekwere, *et al.*, (1989), and Osungbaro, (1990) reported that pap is used as the first native food for weaning babies. It also serves as breakfast meal to pre-school children and adults (Odunfa and Ayedele, 1987). In a more concentrated form; it is boiled into a thick gel and then allowed to stiff in leaf moulds as eko or agidi. In either form, it is usually preferred to many other indigenous fermented foods by the aged and the convalescence. The physical and biochemical properties of Ogi are influenced by the type of cereal grain, fermentation or souring periods and the milling method (Osungbaro, 1990, Hounhouigan *et al.*, 1993).

The importance of cereal grains to the nutrition of millions of people around the world is widely recognized because they make up such a large part of diets in developing countries. Cereals grains cannot be considered only as a source of energy as they provide significant amount of protein as well. It is also recognized that cereal grains have a low protein concentration and the protein quality is limited by deficiencies in some essential amino acids, mainly methionine and lysine much less appreciated, however, is the fact that some cereal grains contain an excess of certain essential amino acids that influence the efficiency of protein utilization. Nutritional compositions of maize per 100g include 69.3% carbohydrate, 8.5% protein, 9.5% moisture, 1.5% minerals and 2.9% crude fiber (Cortez and Wild-Altamin, 1972).

The high fibre content prevents constipation and colorectal cancer. It is believed to contain antioxidants which can neutralize the effects of harmful free radicals that can cause disease like cancer. The antioxidant beta cryptoxanthin prevents lung cancer, while lutein prevents age related vision loss. Antioxidants slow cognitive decline and conditions like Alzheimer’s. it is also believed to contain Vitamin C, E, Thiamine, Phosphorus etc. Vitamin C boosts immunity and fights infections, while the presence of vitamin E gives maize anti-aging properties. The high fiber content is another characteristic linked to the nutritional benefits of maize. This condition makes it suitable for weights lose.

Thiamine is required for boosting memory, cognitive functions and nerve health, and pantothenic acid is essential for energy, as it is linked to carbohydrate, protein and lipid metabolism. Folate is an essential requirement especially during pregnancy. The phosphorus helps to maintain normal growth, kidney, and functions and bone health. Magnesium boosts later, as well as regulates the heart rate. Finally, maize lowers LDL cholesterol and guards against cardiac diseases, diabetes and hypertension.

Commercial complementary foods modified to meet infant nutrient requirements are expensive and beyond the reach of most Nigerian families (Nwamarah and Amadi, 2009; Anigo *et al.*, 2010). Hence many depend on inadequately processed traditional foods consisting mainly of supplemented cereal porridges made from maize, sorghum and millet (Nnam, 2002). However, it has been recorded that approximately 20-50% of the nutrients available in the original cereal grain are lost through processing associated with the loss of the aleurone layer and germ during wet and sieving (Adeyemi, 1983, Akinrele and Bashir 1967). These problems compromise the health, growth and development of infants thereby predisposing them to protein energy malnutrition (PEM) and infections (due to lowered immunity). PEM results when an infant's body need for energy and protein or both are not satisfied by their diets (Wardlaw and Hampl, 2007). So, in order to create awareness on nutrient availability in Ogi and probably reduce the prevalence of malnutrition during the weaning children (under five), this research sort to determine nutrients of pap flour made from yellow maize fortified with naturally sourced raw material.

METHODOLOGY

- **Sources of raw materials**

Dried yellow maize (*Zea mays*), Ginger (*Zingiber officinale*), Turmeric (*Curcuma longo*), Date palm fruit (*Phoenix dactylifera*), Soya beans (*Glycine max*), beetroot (*Beta vulgaris*), mint leaves (*Mentha piperita L-*) and sunflower seeds (*Helianthus annus L*) were purchased from Anyigba market in Kogi State.

- **Equipment**

All equipment were of analytical grade and were obtained from Biochemistry and Food, Nutrition and Home Sciences department, Kogi State University, Anyigba, Kogi State, Nigeria.

- **Sample Preparation**

- **Processing of Fermented Maize Flour**

The yellow maize gains were sorted and cleaned by removing the pest infected grains and discolored ones. It was them steeped for 3days under ambient temperature of ($28\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$). The steep water was decanted and the steeped grains was washed with distilled water and wet milled. It was then wet-sieved using as muslin bag and followed by the souring of the filtrate for 48hrs. After this, the water was decanted and the wet clean sediment (Ogi) was collected in a clean muslin bag and dewatered to obtain a semi-dried porridge and it was sun dried and dry milled and then sieved to obtain a fine powder and packaged in an airtight container prior to analysis.

Figure 1. Flowchart for the processing of Ogi flour

➤ **Processing of Soya Beans (*Glycine Max*) Flour**

The soya beans were sorted and then parboiled for 25 minutes and the hulls were removed. It was then sun-dried and toasted till it appears brownish in colour and then ground into thin powder.

Figure 2: Flowchart for the processing of soya beans flour

➤ **Processing of Ginger (*Zingiber Officinale*) Powder**

Fresh gingers were soaked in water for 10 minutes and was then cleaned and pounded in a mortar and then dried. After proper drying, it was blended into smooth flour.

Figure 3: Flowchart for the processing of ginger powder

➤ **Processing of Turmeric (*Curcuma Longa*) Powder**

Fresh turmeric was soaked in water for 10 minutes and then washed and pounded in a mortar and then dried. After proper drying, it was blended into smooth flour.

Figure 4: Flowchart for the processing of turmeric powder

➤ **Processing of Date Fruit (*Phoenix Dactylifera*) Powder**

The date fruit de-seed and washed, followed by size reduction and drying. After this it was blended into smooth flour.

Figure 5: Flowchart far the processing of date fruit four

➤ **Processing of Mint Leaf (*Mentha Piperita*) Powder**

The mint leaf was washed and dried followed by blending into a smooth powder

Figure 6: Flowchart for the processing of mint leaf powder

➤ **Processing of Beetroot (*Beta Vulgaris*) Powder**

The beetroot was washed, peeled, sliced into thin layers, dried and then blended into powder,

Figure 7: Flowchart for the processing of beetroot (*Beta vulgaris*) powder

➤ **Processing of Sunflower Seed (*Helianthus Annus*) Powder**
It was toasted, shelled and blended.

Figure 8: Flowchart for the processing of sunflower seed powder

- **Blend Formulation**

The following four formulations were made according to the table 1 below; each value is in percentage.

Table 1: types of formulation

	MAIZE FLOUR	SOYA BEAN	DATE	SUNFLOWER SEED	TURMERIC	BEEETROOT	GINGER	MINT LEAVES
CMFSA	100	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
MFSB	45	2 5	1 7	9	0.25	0.25	3	0 . 5
MFSC	50	2 0	1 7	9	-	0.5	3	0 . 5
MFSD	55	1 5	1 7	9	0 . 5	-	3	0 . 5

- **Preparation of pap from formulated samples**

100g of the powder was reconstituted into slurry by adding water and then poured in boiling water and allowed to gel on fire for 2 minutes.

- **Analytical Method**

Proximate composition: The moisture content, ash, fibre, fat and total carbohydrates were determined by AOAC (2000).

Determination of mineral elements: The mineral content of the blends was analyzed AAS using the method described by Adeyeye and Adewoke (1992).

Determination of anti-nutritional factors: Trypsin inhibitor, phytates, tannins, oxalate, total alkaloid was determined by AOAC (2000)

- **Sensory Evaluation**

The fortified instant 'Ogi' was made into slurry by adding water till it formed a paste and was poured in boiling water on fire and stirred continuously till it became viscous and formed a gruel. The products were evaluated for taste, visual colour, flavour, texture, and choice of sample by a panel of 30 members using a 7-point Hedonic scale The rating of the samples ranged from 1 (dislike very much) to 7 (like very much).

- **Statistical Analysis**

All the data obtained were subjected to statistical analysis using Analysis of variance (ANOVA) and the means were separated using Turkey's test at 5% significance level (SPSS version 20.0 computer software was used).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Proximate analysis is a demonstration of the nutrients present in a food sample. The result shows that the pap flour made from yellow maize incorporated with certain percentage of soya beans, sunflower seed, ginger, beetroot, turmeric, mint leaf and date fruit powder contains significant amount of protein, moisture, ash, crude fiber, carbohydrate, fat and minerals needed by the body.

The result of the moisture content shows that the samples contain tolerable amount of moisture. Hence, the samples can be kept for some period before spoilage occurs. It has been reported that low moisture content in foods helps to improve the storage capacity (Igbian and Akpapunam, 2005). The increase in ash content may be due to the fact that all the raw materials used in fortifying the Ogi flour were rich in considerable amount of essential minerals, so this helped to replace the minerals originally concentrated in the bran and germ of maize but lost during wet sieving process of the Ogi. The ash content represents the total mineral contents in food and thus, serves as a viable tool for nutritional evaluation (Lienel, 2002). The use of sunflower seed and soya beans increased the fat content with increase in the blend of the samples. The sunflower seed is rich in Vitamin E and several minerals needed by the body. It is also rich in Vitamin B and minerals which help to protect the body against diseases The amount of fat present in this blend is adequate due to the fact that any diet that provides 1-2% of its caloric of energy as fat is said to be sufficient to human beings (Anita *et al.*, 2006). Dietary fiber is the constituent of plant cell wall (Mac-Dougall, 1995). Consumption of higher levels of fiber result in reduced risk of cardiovascular diseases and possibly, colon cancer. (Jenkins *et al.*, 2001). It is more significant in resolving the problem of constipation, diabetes, diverticulosis and obesity using (Roberfroid, 1993). The crude fibre values observed were within the values reported by Achimugu and Emmanuel (2021) in the study of tender leaves of fresh and shade dried Black-eyed beans.

In the formulated pap flour, there was increase in the level of protein with increase in level of blend, this could be due to high protein value of soya beans. Soya beans being a very good source of protein helps to building the body, especially, infant and adult. This is in line with the report of Solomon (2005) that blending of cereals and legumes that complement each other increase the protein content. The inclusion of legume and additives in different proportions was associated with decrease in carbohydrates contents of maize Ogi. In comparing the processed Ogi flour with the prepared Pap, the carbohydrates, protein and the mineral element of the processed flour was higher than that observed in prepared pap made from the flour, this could be due to concentration effect. however, the value observed is lower than the report by Mbata, *et al.*, 2009 on the study of maize Ogi fortified with legume.

Table 2: Proximate composition of processed pap flour incorporated with natural additives.

Sample	Moisture	Ash	Crude Fiber	F a t	Protein	Carbohydrate
%	%	%	%	%	%	%
CMFSA	5.66±0.07 ^a	4.79±0.06 ^a	6.09±0.08 ^a	2.03±0.03 ^a	4.35±0.06 ^a	78.09±1.11 ^c
MFSB	10.00±0.39 ^b	8.47±0.03 ^b	10.77±0.42 ^b	3.59±0.14 ^b	7.69±0.30 ^b	59.48±1.57 ^b
MFSC	11.46±0.17 ^c	9.67±0.15 ^c	12.34±0.19 ^c	4.11±0.06 ^c	8.82±0.13 ^c	53.57±0.70 ^a
MFSD	12.22±0.20 ^c	10.35±0.17 ^c	13.17±0.21 ^c	4.39±0.07 ^c	9.40±0.15 ^c	50.47±0.80 ^a

Values are expressed as Mean ± Standard Deviation. Values with different superscript down the column are significantly different. P value less than 0.05 (p < 0.05) is significant.

CMFSA (Control Maize flour sample A, 100%).

MFSB (maize flour sample B, 55%, sunflower seed 9%, soya beans 15%, ginger 3%, turmeric 0.25, mint leaf 0.5%, and Date leaf 17%).

MFSC (maize flour sample C, 50%, soya beans 20%, sunflower seed 9%, ginger 3%, beetroot 0.5%, mint leaf 0.5%, date fruit 17%).

MFSD (maize flour sample D, 45%, soya beans flour 25%, sunflower seed 9%, ginger 3%, mint leaf 0.05%, turmeric 0.25% beetroot 0.25% and date fruit 17%).

The is significant increase in mineral elements in the samples fortified with natural additives in both the processed maize flour and the prepared pap made from the flour, this is in-line with the assertion that addition of spices such as ginger, mint, beetroot to yellow maize gruel influence mineral content, with specific combinations resulting in higher potassium and magnesium levels (FOA 2000). The mineral elements in processed maize flour were higher than the prepared pap, this could be due to concentration effect. Its high mineral value suggests a rich mineral source. The low mineral value of maize (control CMFA) implies that infants fed on maize gruel alone are at risk of micronutrient deficiency especially iron, zinc and calcium.

Most of the materials used for the supplementation of maize "Ogi" were underutilized and this study shows that the utilization of these food materials as a constituent of traditional weaning meal and enriched adult gruel helps to improve the nutritional values of Ogi. Date fruit is a natural sweetener which prevents the risk of diabetes unlike refined sugars, Mineral elements are important in normal metabolic activities in human. It also helps to prevent some diseases and other

ailments. Manganese deficiency results in abnormal skeletal development in human and a number of animals. Manganese is the preferred cofactor of enzymes called glycosyltransferases these enzymes are required for the synthesis of proteoglycans that are needed for the formation of healthy cartilage and bones (Keen *et al.*, 1996). Calcium plays a role in mediating the constriction and relaxation of blood vessels (vasoconstriction and vasodilatation), nerve impulse transmission, muscle contraction, bone formation and the secretion of hormones like insulin (Weaver *et al.*, 2012).

Copper is a critical functional component of several essential enzymes known as cuproenzyme (Prohaska, 2011). The cuproenzyme, tyrosinase, is required for the formation of the pigment melanin. Melanin is formed in cells called melanocytes and plays a role in the pigmentation of the hair, skin, and eyes (Turnlund *et al.*, 2006) Iron is the fourth most abundant element of Earth's crust and one of the best studied micronutrients in nutrition science (Aggett *et al.*, 2012 and Wessling-Resick *et al.*, 2014). It is a key element in the metabolism of all living organisms. Haemoglobin is the primary protein found in red blood cells and represents about two-thirds of the body's iron. The vital role of hemoglobin is transporting oxygen from the lungs to the rest of the body and this is derived from its unique ability to acquire oxygen rapidly during the short time it spends in contact with the lungs and to release oxygen as needed during its circulation through the tissues. Magnesium plays a structural role in bone, cell membranes, and chromosomes (Rude *et al.*, 2006). A number of studies indicate that groups with relatively high dietary potassium intakes have lower blood pressures than comparable groups with relatively low potassium intakes (Curhan *et al.*, 1997).

Because sodium is the primary determinant of extracellular fluid volume, including blood volume, a number of physiological mechanisms that regulate blood volume and blood pressure work by adjusting the body's sodium content. In the circulatory system, pressure receptors (bar receptors) sense changes in blood pressure and send excitatory or inhibitory signals to the nervous system and/or endocrine glands to affect sodium regulation by the kidneys. In general sodium retention results in water retention, and sodium loss results in water loss (Bailey *et al.*, 2014). Zinc plays important roles in growth and development, the immune response, neurological function, and reproduction. The significant amount of mineral element observed is an indication that the fortified Ogi could reduce high prevalence of mineral element deficiencies among pregnant women and children of under- five.

Table 3: Mean mineral element composition of processed pap flour incorporated with natural additives

Calcium (mg)	Copper (mg)	Iron (mg)	Magnesium (mg)	Manganese (mg)	Potassium (mg)	Sodium (mg)	Zinc (mg)
0.24±0.00 ^a	0.19±0.00 ^a	26.10±0.34 ^a	1.22±0.22 ^a	0.70±0.01 ^a	0.45±0.06 ^a	2.18±0.03 ^a	2.21±0.03 ^a
0.43±0.02 ^b	0.33±0.01 ^b	46.17±1.79 ^b	2.15±0.0 ^b	1.23±0.05 ^b	0.72±0.03 ^b	3.85±0.15 ^b	3.95±0.15 ^b
0.49±0.01 ^c	0.38±0.01 ^c	52.9±0.80 ^c	2.47±0.04 ^c	1.41±0.02 ^c	0.82±0.01 ^b	4.41±0.07 ^c	4.52±0.07 ^c
0.53±0.01 ^c	0.40±0.01 ^c	57.92±1.22 ^c	2.63±0.04 ^c	1.51±0.02 ^c	0.88±0.01 ^c	4.70±0.07 ^c	4.82±0.08 ^c

Values are expressed as Mean ± Standard Deviation. Values with different superscript down the column are significantly different. P value less than 0.05 (p<0.05) is significant.

Table 4: Mean mineral element composition of prepared pap incorporated with natural additives.

Sample	Calcium (mg)	Copper (mg)	Iron (mg)	Magnesium (mg)	Manganese (mg)	Potassium (mg)	Zinc (mg)
CMFSA	0.16±0.00 ^a	0.14±0.00 ^a	20.08±0.26 ^a	0.87±0.0 ^a	1.11±0.01 ^a	0.34±0.00 ^a	1.45±0.02
MFBS	0.29±0.01 ^b	0.25±0.01 ^b	35.51±1.38 ^b	1.54±0.06 ^b	1.97±0.08 ^b	0.60±0.02 ^b	1.82±0.03
MFSC	0.33±0.00 ^c	0.29±0.00 ^c	40.69±0.61 ^c	1.76±0.03 ^c	2.26±0.03 ^c	0.69±0.01 ^c	2.94±0.04
MFSD	0.35±0.01 ^c	0.31±0.00 ^c	43.40±0.70 ^c	1.88±0.03 ^c	2.41±0.04 ^c	0.73±0.01 ^c	3.13±0.05

Values are expressed as Mean ± Standard Deviation. Values with different superscript down the column are significantly different. P value less than 0.05 (p<0.05) is significant.

Anti-nutrients are natural or synthetic compounds found in a variety of foods especially grains, beans, legumes and nuts that interfere with the absorption of vitamins, minerals and other nutrients. Fermentation (48-72 hours) and germination/sprouting can enhance mineral availability by reducing antinutrients like phytates, which otherwise chelate divalent cations and limit the absorption of iron and zinc, they can even get in the way of the digestive enzymes, which are keys for proper absorption. An increase in glucoside level was observed in the samples, this could be attributed to the presence of soya beans, sunflower seed and maize flour which have some amount of glucoside. The increase in oxalate content may be due to the addition of soya beans and other materials used in the supplementation which have content of oxalate. This finding is in correlation with the report of IJarotimi and Esho (2009). The removal of the seed coat of soaked maize and soya beans may be attributed to the low level of phytate content. The increase in the total alkaloids content may be due to the presence of soya beans with high content of alkaloids, however, the level is within the acceptable level of 50-200 microgram/kg by FAO. The anti-nutrients determined however are within the acceptable range recommended reported by Siddhuraju and Becker (2001).

The essence of cooking or boiling food is to make the food soft, remove heat liable anti-nutrients or make food less toxic to man and make nutrients more available. The addition of the additives increases anti-nutrients in the processed pap flour; however, it was lower in prepared pap made from the flour, the significant reduction in anti-nutrients in the prepared pap may be as a result of effect of heat. This result is in line with the findings of Embaby (2010). The moisture content of the prepared pap was higher than the processed flour due to the addition of water in the process of pap preparation. The substantial availability of this nutrients is an indication that adequately fortified maize (Ogi) is rich in nutrients which could be potent in preventing mineral nutrient deficiencies in pregnant women and weaned children (children of under-five).

Table 5: Result of anti-nutrient composition of processed pap flour incorporated with natural additives

Sample	Total Alkaloid-s (g/100g)	Glucosides	Hermaggl-utinin (p p m)	Oxalate (p p m)	Phytates (p p m)	Saponins (p p m)	Tanins (p p m)	Trypsin Inhibitor
CMFSA	10.00±0.13 ^a	6.74±0.09 ^a	0.06±0.00 ^a	2.90±0.04 ^a	2.83±0.04 ^a	3.26±0.04 ^a	1.76±0.02 ^a	3.48±0.09 ^a
MFBSB	17.70±0.69 ^b	11.93±0.4 ^b	0.10±0.00 ^b	5.13±0.20 ^b	5.00±0.19 ^b	5.77±0.2 ^b	3.08±0.12 ^b	6.16±0.24 ^b
MFSC	20.29±0.28 ^c	13.66±0.21 ^c	0.11±0.00 ^c	5.88±0.09 ^c	5.73±0.09 ^c	6.71±0.24 ^c	3.53±0.05 ^c	7.04±0.11 ^c
MFSD	21.63±0.35 ^c	14.58±0.23 ^c	0.12±0.00 ^c	6.27±0.10 ^c	6.11±0.10 ^c	7.05±0.11 ^c	3.76±0.00 ^c	7.52±0.12 ^c

Values are expressed as Mean ± Standard Deviation. Values with different superscript down the column are significantly different. P value less than 0.05 (p<0.05) is significant.

Table 6: Result of anti-nutrient composition of prepared pap incorporated with natural additives.

Sample	Total Alkaloid-s (g/100g)	Glucosides	Hermagglutinin (ppm)	Oxalate (p p m)	Phytates (p p m)	Saponin (p p m)	Tanins (p p m)	Trypsin Inhibitor (ppm)
CMFSA	8.34±0.11 ^a	5.61±0.08 ^a	0.04±0.00 ^a	2.42±0.03 ^a	2.57±0.03 ^a	2.97±0.04 ^a	1.45±0.02 ^a	3.16±0.04 ^a
MFBSB	14.79±0.52 ^b	9.94±0.39 ^b	0.08±0.00 ^b	4.28±0.17 ^b	4.55±0.18 ^b	5.25±0.20 ^b	2.57±0.10 ^b	5.60±0.22 ^b
MFSC	16.90±0.25 ^c	11.39±0.17 ^c	0.09±0.00 ^c	4.90±0.17 ^c	5.21±0.08 ^c	6.01±0.09 ^c	2.94±0.04 ^c	6.41±0.10 ^c
MFSD	18.02±0.29 ^c	12.15±0.19 ^c	0.09±0.00 ^c	5.22±0.08 ^c	5.58±0.09 ^c	6.41±0.10 ^c	3.13±0.05 ^c	6.84±0.11 ^c

Values are expressed as Mean ± Standard Deviation. Values with different superscript down the column are significantly different. P value less than 0.05 (p<0.05) is significant

The findings from sensory evaluation shows that the 30 semi-untrained panelists preferred the prepared Pap from processed maize flour incorporated with natural additives in this order; Sample B, D and C compared to the 100% maize flour for colour, flavor, texture, consistency and taste. Fermentation and roasting add flavour to food and these may have influenced the colour, flavor, texture, consistency and taste of the gruels, this complements Onoja and Obizoba (2009) which reported high acceptability of 24 hours fermented blends as a result of improved flavour and mutual supplementation.

Table 7: Result of Sensory Evaluation of prepared Pap Incorporated with Natural Additives.

S a m p l e	C o l o u r	T e x t u r e	T a s t e	F l a v o u r	C o n s i s t e n c y
C M F S A	5.30±1.26 ^a	5.87±0.82 ^a	4.40±1.94 ^a	4.30±1.62 ^a	5.87±1.11 ^a
M F S B	6.47±0.78 ^b	6.57±0.63 ^b	6.60±0.62 ^b	6.73±0.52 ^b	6.50±0.68 ^b
M F S C	5.77±1.17 ^a	5.90±1.03 ^a	5.90±0.84 ^b	6.10±1.06 ^b	5.90±0.99 ^a
M F S D	6.33±1.12 ^b	6.40±0.72 ^b	6.27±0.94 ^b	6.17±1.05 ^b	6.23±1.10 ^a

Values are expressed as Mean ± Standard Deviation. Values with different superscript down the column are significantly different. P value less than 0.05 (p<0.05) is significant.

CONCLUSION

The research shows a substantial amount of nutrients (Protein, minerals) in the samples fortified with natural additives compared to the control sample and the values were higher in the processed flour sample than the prepared pap sample made from the flour.

The anti-nutritional factors (alkaloids, tannin, saponins etc.) are known for their anti-inflammatory, antibiotic and anti-aging properties, but relatively high amount is associated with inhibition of mineral nutrients absorption. The anti-nutrients observed in this research were higher in the processed flour than the prepared pap from the flour, however, it is within the acceptable level. The Sensory Assessment test proves that Ogi with MFSB (55% maize flour, 15% soy beans, 9% sunflower seed, 17% date fruit, 0.5% mint leaf, 0.25 turmeric, and 3% ginger) was rated best.

- **Recommendations**

Fortifying locally made yellow maize-Pap (Ogi or Akamu) with natural additives is a nutritionally effective method in boosting the nutritional value of fermented cereal porridge, making it suitable for children's growth, healthy weight gain for adults, the sick and convalescence and above all, reducing high dependence on expensive foreign food products.

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